

Salient Sights and Sounds: Comparing Visual and Auditory Stimuli Remembrance using Audio Set Ontology and Sonic Mapping

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ABSTRACT

In this study, we explore how store customers recall their perceptual experience with a focus on comparing the remembrance of auditory and visual stimuli. The study was carried out using a novel mixed-methods approach that involved Deep Hanging Out, field study and interviews, including drawing sonic mind maps. The data collected was analysed using thematic analysis, sound classification with the Audio Set ontology, counting occurrences of different auditory and visual elements attended in the store, and rating the richness of their descriptions. The results showed that sights were more salient than sounds and that participants recalled music more frequently compared to the Deep Hanging Out observations, but remembered fewer varieties of sounds in general.

1. INTRODUCTION

Retail environments provide to customers a plethora of stimuli through a variety of channels; one can see, hear, smell, taste, and feel their way through a shopping trip as a matter of course. The many environmental aspects that combine to create a *servicescape* have been known to impact the shopping experience in numerous ways, including enjoyment, time spent in the store and amount of money spent [1]. Another aspect of the effect of a servicescape on a customer is how they remember it.

While studies on customer experiences are not uncommon, how people recall their experiences has seen limited research [2], and even less with specific regard to the perception of sights and sounds. This study aimed to explore the sights and sounds of a retail environment and how customers remember them and their experiences. Through observations, ‘Deep Hanging Out’ (see [3]) and interviews with participants, we investigated the acoustic and visual stimuli present in a particular servicescape, and how these were perceived and remembered during a store visit.

The first phase of this study focused on the observations of the researchers on individual visits to a chosen retail location, a combined clothing and homeware store in central Stockholm. These observations informed the line of questioning carried out in our second research phase, which involved inviting participants to visit the store and afterwards

gathering data about their experiences. The information from these two phases was then used to compare recollections of sights and sounds. By employing this novel mixed methods approach, combining field study with an auto-ethnographic method, the present study provides new knowledge about how this type of experiential analysis can be carried out.

2. BACKGROUND

2.1 Retail Environments

The dimensions of the retail environment are described by Bitner [1] as the signs and artefacts, the space and its function, and the ambient conditions. These combine to create a holistic perception of the servicescape and influence customers’ feelings and actions, for example, the familiarity of ambient music affecting the perception of time spent in the store [1, 4]. Ward et al. [5] suggested that people’s memories and feelings about their experiences are affected by their purpose for being there. In research specific to memories of shopping environments [2], four dimensions of customer recollections are proposed: a customer’s overall attraction to the store; the structure of the memory; affective aspects perceived during the memory; and sense of belonging to a social group. The study suggests that retail environments leverage ambient conditions like lighting and music to enhance the affective dimension of memory, which they correlate with customer satisfaction.

Hynes and Manson [6] carried out a study of sounds, particularly music, within supermarkets and how it affected customers. They documented the soundscapes of these stores and, through semi-structured interviews, gathered accounts of what customers perceived during their shopping trips. On separate days on a weekend and weekday, they observed ambient noises within the stores and recorded sound levels. Interviews with customers intercepted leaving the store suggested that while they had very low awareness of music played in the supermarket, it may still impact their mood and behaviour without their conscious awareness. They posit that music is a potentially unwanted distraction within the supermarket environment, as customers are focusing their attention on shopping, and may even limit customers’ decision-making abilities. Low awareness of music in the above study may well be explained by *inattentional awareness*, a concept describing low perception of irrelevant stimuli when executing a task with high perceptual load [7].

In a series of experiments, we have seen that customers

visiting a virtual store remain unaware of present interaction sounds unless instructed to listen for them [8, 9]. Even sounds that were designed to be incongruent with the servicescape (for instance bird chirps and a clown horn) went largely unnoticed. However, among participants that were instructed about the presence of interactive sound, there was a preference for congruent sounds over incongruent ones.

2.2 Soundscape Analysis

The perceptions of soundscapes in public spaces, and the factors that can influence them, were analysed by Marry and Defrance [10]. They proposed that these spaces could be subject to “synesthetic” perception, which involves two or more interacting sensory modalities. Their research gathered data from photographs, mind maps, and interviews with participants. They describe the use of mind maps in prior acoustic and environmental research, suggesting that they can document both aural and visual impressions of a space. In their analysis, the authors emphasise the connection between the senses in evaluating perception, noting that the acoustic environment must be viewed as a relationship between all sensory functions. They describe a detrimental effect of visual attention on hearing perception and vice versa and thus consider the impact of visual elements in the space on the perception and evaluation of the soundscape.

When evaluating the results of an acoustic experiment, the source of sounds must be considered [11]. While describing sounds and their sources may seem straightforward for interviewees, they will nonetheless often provide ambiguous responses as to their origin [12]. Slightly different sound constructions can have different effects on human perception. As such, when interviewees try to simulate a specific sound through vocal imitation, they produce a caricature or “cartoon sound” [11] which only captures some of the relevant features. Imitation is also ineffective for describing unidentifiable sounds [12]. Therefore, it is important that we attempt to define the sources of sounds within this study, more than simply the sounds themselves.

The Audio Set ontology proposed by Gemmeke et al. [13] could be one way to define everyday sounds and their sources [14]. The ontology was based on systematised categorisation according to the description of the sound and distributing it into a specific field. In this, sounds are divided into seven main categories. For example music, animals, sounds of things, and human sounds. These categories include classes of sound events and are described in detail, for instance, the category ‘sounds of things’ includes engines, vehicles, tools, and more.¹

2.3 Auditory Memory

Cohen et al. [15] found large differences in short-term recall and recognition of auditory and visual stimuli and concluded that auditory memory is systematically inferior to visual memory, even with rich audio material such as music and semantic contents. In their study, participants had

78% correct recognition from 64 auditory objects, while Shepard [16] reported 98% recognition for 600 visual objects. Based on two possible explanations—that auditory objects are fundamentally different from visual and that the auditory (short-term) memory is smaller—they hypothesise an asymmetry between visual and auditory processing. The studies consider recollection of novel items among a data set participants had been exposed to. It is speculated that auditory memory is better at recognising classes of sounds (such as musical elements, objects belonging to the same group) than the exact sounds used in the experiment.

3. METHOD

Two phases of study were carried out: Deep Hanging Out (see [3, 17]), and a field study. Through location scouting, we selected the research site and then conducted Deep Hanging Out to collect initial experiences of the shop and to record sound environment data. Based on the first study outcome, we prepared the second study materials and invited participants to join a 10-minute visit to the shop followed by an interview. The data from the two studies were integrated and compared during the data analysis process.

3.1 Location Scouting

The location scouting aimed to find a suitable store to carry out the subsequent studies. It was desirable that the store had the following characteristics: located in the city centre of Stockholm, only has one floor, sells gender-neutral products, etc., to facilitate participant recruitment and testing. Scouting was conducted during the weekend in Stockholm city centre, with basic information documented about the visited shops. After discussing each shop’s characteristics, one combined clothing and homeware store was selected as the research site because it was located in a popular shopping centre, with additional advantages including easy access, only one floor, high traffic, and selling gender-neutral products.

3.2 Deep Hanging Out

The formal studies started with Deep Hanging Out, a structured observation method that was developed by applying techniques from anthropology [18]. Instead of inviting participants, researchers themselves act as the customers and visit the shop to collect structured data with a list of focal points [19] as a guideline, and draw a map of the shop to be used in the subsequent field study stage.

Three of the authors and an additional researcher were involved in the individual Deep Hanging Out. The researchers were divided into two groups, one visiting the shop on weekdays and another on weekends, to ensure the result was more generalisable. Acting as customers, researchers went shopping while paying closer attention to the sound environment. The researchers used phones to record salient sounds, measure decibels of different locations, and take pictures of salient visual elements.

A modified table of 12 focal points [19] was used as a reference to write down the observations, including Family and kids, Food and drinks, Built environment, Posses-

¹ See also AudioSet, an online dataset for exploring sound events: <https://research.google.com/audioset/index.html>

sions, Media consumption, Tools and Technology, Demographics, Traffic, Information and communication access, Sound and visual elements, Overall experience, and Other. This helped achieve deep insights into the selected store and obtained revealing data which could assist in designing the interview questions for the following study.

After finishing Deep Hanging Out, each researcher drew a shop map highlighting the visual and audio salient elements and filling the focal point table. Based on the raw data, the second study interview questions list and blank sonic mind map were created. The data from Deep Hanging Out was further processed with the second study's data for comparison.

3.3 Field Study

In the next step, we continued the research with a field study, in which the same researchers guided participants to visit the shop individually and interviewed them about the visual and audible salient stimuli during regular shopping. The purpose of the field study was to understand how customers feel about sound and visual stimuli and how these two different types of elements affected each other.

Fourteen participants, accessed by convenience sampling, participated in the field study which consisted of a store visit, an undisclosed recollection task, and an interview. First, the researchers introduced the field study in which each participant was instructed to spend ten minutes in the store and try to find something they wanted to buy. Following the visit, they would be accompanied to a nearby coffee shop and get a drink as an incentive for participating in the interview. After the store visit and before the interview the participants were asked to fill in a sonic mind map, a technique used in acoustic research, to show their instant impression of the visit [10]. Participants drew or wrote down what they most remember seeing or hearing when filling in the sonic mind map. The interview consisted of 13 questions with additional follow-up questions and collected qualitative data which focused on the audible and visible elements in the store that impressed the participants. Four questions collected data on participants' shopping behaviour, general experience and current mood.

3.4 Sound Item Classification

The data collected in the field study has two main parts, the interview transcript and the sonic mind map. The data analysis process was divided into two parts: managing data and comparing differences. For the transcript, the thematic analysis method was used to code and categorise the transcript into different themes [20], which showed an overview of the interview outcomes. Moreover, for further discussion, content related to sound was categorised into three layers: sounds mentioned without being asked, sounds mentioned after being asked, and recollections of sounds based on visual stimuli. Each sound item was labelled into two levels based on the Audio Set 'Sunburst' diagram [13, 14], and the number and percentage of each category (*Sounds of things*, *Human sounds*, *Music*, and *Channel, environment and background*) were counted.

The sounds recorded in the Deep Hanging Out research were also processed in the same way as for interview data. In order to distinguish which is more salient, the researchers rated the richness of the descriptions of auditory and visual items using a 5-point Likert scale and marked the attitudes (positive, neutral, or negative), and the mean score was calculated for comparison. Regarding the sonic mind map, the information was categorised into two sections: *general* and *sound*, and the number of occurrences of each item was counted. When the raw data processing was finished, data visualisation graphs were created to compare the results of the different sound layers, studies, and sound classifications.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Deep Hanging Out

Four Deep Hanging Out sessions were completed; two on a weekday and two on a weekend, all during midday. On both weekday and weekend sessions the average audio level across the store was recorded as 61 dB: above 70 dB in the loudest areas, and less than 50 dB in the quietest (see Fig. 2). Fourteen loudspeakers playing music could be seen and heard throughout the store, observably loudest in the centre area.

Maps drawn after the observation recorded seven types of sound-specific recollections across nine entries, and 32 recollections unrelated to sound across 77 entries (see examples in Fig. 2). Analysis of the four written observations showed 26 (39 with duplicates) unique reported sound recollections (see Table 1). The most common sounds were classified as *Sounds of things*, accounting for 25 of these recollections, while the next most common classifications were *Human sounds* (8), *Music* (4), and *Environment and background* (2). Sounds of things could be further classified into seven subcategories: Specific impact sounds (11), Mechanism (6), Wood (6), Alarm (5), Glass (3), Tools (2), and Miscellaneous (2).

4.2 Participants Study

Recollections given by participants were divided into three layers which represented different hierarchical levels of attention: Layer 1 consisted of initial recollections of sounds after leaving the store; layer 2 were recollections of sounds in response to being directly asked about the sounds in the shop; and layer 3 were recollections of sounds related to specific visual stimuli when asked to recall what the participant had seen. Figure 3 shows the distribution of recollections across categories and layers.

Participants' mind maps included fewer and less varied sound-specific recollections than general, non-audio recollections. Fourteen types of non-audio recollections were provided over 69 entries on the mind maps, compared to six types of sound-specific recollections from 16 entries. On average, the richness (in terms of detail) of descriptions provided for sights was greater than that of sounds. Sound descriptions were basic, whereas participants provided rich descriptions of sights. Attitudes towards the recollections between sights and sounds were also similar, with 64% of

Figure 1. Blank sonic mind map used for recollection of sound and visual events in the store during interviews.

Figure 2. Sonic map with sound annotations from the Deep Hanging Out. The elements of the shop and corresponding sound levels are labelled from the field study.

Bowl clashing	Beeping sound at the cashier	Fridge
Staff typing on computer	“A lot of noises”	Dishes clinking from cafe next door
Freezer noise	Cuckoo clock	Doors slamming
Door close and open	Air conditioner	Sounds of wooden bowls
Walking on wooden floor in high heels	Escalator sound	Paper crumpling sounds
Employees using walkie talkies	Beeping - staff using a device	General footsteps
Sound of shopping carts	Clothes hangers	Squeaky door
Cashier: beeping sound, scanning barcodes, printing receipts	Quiet ambiance	People talking to each other
	Child banging plastic sign on wooden table	Background music: bagpipes, violins, chiming, calm and peaceful

Table 1. Sound recollections (26) from written observations after four Deep Hanging Out sessions.

Figure 3. Sound recollection counts across five categories from 14 participants in three hierarchical layers: (1) their initial recollection, (2) when prompted about sound, (3) from visual impressions.

sounds and 57% of sight recollections being positive, and 35% of both being neutral. Overall, 16 individual visual salient recollections were provided by participants, compared to only ten acoustic salient recollections. All except two participants said that they remembered sights more clearly than sounds. In addition to auditory and visual impressions, 35% of the participants recalled another sense perception, such as smell or touch, without being prompted by the interviewer.

In both initial recollections (layer 1) and when directly asked about sounds (layer 2), music was the most common memory across participants, mentioned in 50% of initial recollections of their experience and in 39% of responses to direct questions about sounds (see Fig. 3). Human sounds were the second most common response. When directly asked about sounds they remembered or sounds associated with visual stimuli, participants mentioned more specific sounds of things than in their initial recollections. Other sounds recalled included environmental (or background) and source-ambiguous sounds. Some participants mentioned that they felt that the music in the store was effective for masking other environmental noises in the store.

As mentioned, most participants reported enjoying the store’s sound environment. When asked what sounds they found unpleasant within a servicescape in general, partic-

Figure 4. Proportions of recollections from the sonic mind map (layer 1), interview data (layer 2) and Deep Hanging Out.

ipants reported that pop music, intense music and loud sounds were the most disturbing. Participants frequently mentioned a couple of other very popular shops by their name that, in their opinion, have these unpleasant acoustic environments.

4.3 Analysis

In both the mindmap and interview analysis it is clear that sights are more salient than sounds in this situation, as was self-reported by participants. It is evident that sounds remembered by participants differ from the sounds reported in the Deep Hanging Out observations (see Fig. 4). Compared to Deep Hanging Out, participants recalled far fewer varieties of sounds of things. Music accounted for a greater proportion of participants’ recollections than those of the Deep Hanging Out sessions, with 50% and 39% of reports in layers 1 and 2 respectively, compared to 10% of recollections in Deep Hanging Out. Environmental sounds were also more frequently recalled by participants, accounting for 12% and 10% of layers 1 and 2 respectively, compared with 5% of recollections in Deep Hanging Out. Human sounds were reported in similar proportions in both cases, accounting for 25%, 32%, and 20% in layers 1 and 2 and Deep Hanging Out, respectively.

5. DISCUSSION

5.1 Task-Specificity

The distinct differences between the Deep Hanging Out observations and participant reports suggest a connection between the perception and remembrance of stimuli and their relevance to the task at hand. Participants were tasked with finding something they would like to buy, while the purpose of the Deep Hanging Out was to observe the sights and sounds of the servicescape. Participant reports showed that the best remembered stimuli were those which were relevant to the task of shopping. Visual memories of products and memories of the atmosphere of the store, including decor and music, were the most universal, and all allude to what is most important to the participants while shopping. The difference between these reports and the Deep Hanging Out observation shows that while there are many other stimuli within this particular servicescape, these are extraneous to shoppers. This inattentive awareness may be a cause of the diminished perception and remembrance of these other stimuli.

5.2 How People Think about Sound

Compared with Deep Hanging Out, music was clearly the most noticed and remembered sound reported by participants. People naturally associate music, and even human sounds like talking, with listening. By contrast, they may not think of sounds of objects or ambient noise when asked about or casually describing a sound environment. Along with the effects of perception and memory, this association may have influenced this result. In addition to frequency, the depth and richness of descriptions recorded could imply a difference in perception of visual and auditory stimuli. However, it is worth noting that some people may simply find it easier to describe visual stimuli than sounds, similar to other sensory perceptions that may be easy to perceive but difficult to describe, like smell or touch. Furthermore, these results could allude to limitations on how vividly people can remember these elusive stimuli.

5.3 The Mutual Effects of Sights and Sounds

As mentioned above, the task of shopping may have impacted memories of stimuli. In the studied store specifically, the sounds of products are largely irrelevant, as their function is primarily visual or utilitarian. It has been suggested in previous research that focus on visual stimuli may reduce perception of auditory stimuli. As such, in a store like this, it is feasible that customers' attentive listening is limited while shopping. Participant reports of unknown sounds were often accompanied by accounts of seeking visual identification of the sound source. By comparison, there were no reports of participants seeking a sound to associate with visual stimuli. This could indicate a preference towards visual perception, an inclination to store memories of stimuli visually, or be suggestive of a natural instinct, and suggests a unilateral relationship between sight and sound in this situation. Similarly, when participants reported *sounds of things*, it was largely in connection to visual memory. This could suggest that a

link to visual stimuli may improve the memory of an otherwise irrelevant or forgotten sound. It is clear that the servicescape of the studied store, with particular regards to sound, has been well designed to help people focus on the task of shopping. By creating a good atmosphere and limiting sound distractions, customers are better able to focus on the visual stimuli within the store.

6. CONCLUSION

In the results of this study, it is clear that for participants within the servicescape of the store, sights, the visual stimuli, were more salient than sounds. People are less likely to notice and remember sound stimuli while shopping, but when well used, music can support a pleasant shopping experience.

6.1 Learnings for Sound Designers

Servicescape sound designers can take from this study that when properly used, music can support the store's ambiance. Distracting music should be avoided to allow customers to focus on shopping. Moreover, the acoustic environment can be leveraged to mask sounds irrelevant to shopping, ensuring that negative or otherwise distracting sounds are not salient and do not disturb the customer. Overall, when designing for a servicescape which has a focus on visual or functional products, avoiding overstimulating customers with sound can help them better perceive products and the environment.

6.2 Further Research

Sights and sounds are just a part of the holistic perception of a shopping environment. While this study suggests that sights are more salient and better remembered than sounds, the interactions between more modes of perception are worthy of further research. Perceptions and memories of sounds with relation to touch, smell and taste may provide deeper insight into how we experience and remember stimuli. This study was unable to produce a clear answer to the effect of attitude on memory. In these results, memories of salient stimuli are more clearly linked to their relevance to the participants than their attitude toward them. However, more research is needed to further specify the effects. Future studies may consider analysing a variety of sounds of similar relevance to a participant to control for this. The chosen sound classification method posed some challenges for analysis in this study and its use could be improved upon in further research. Applying the Audio Set ontology, which is a broad and comprehensive collection of sounds, to the relatively narrow context of a single indoor environment necessitated careful classification of some borderline sounds favour the clusters most relevant to the present context. Future applications of this ontology may improve on this naive approach.

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7. REFERENCES

- [1] M. J. Bitner, "Servicescapes: The impact of physical surroundings on customers and employees," *Journal of Marketing*, vol. 56, no. 2, pp. 57–71, 1992.
- [2] M. Flacandji and N. Krey, "Remembering shopping experiences: The shopping experience memory scale," *Journal of Business Research*, vol. 107, pp. 279–289, 2020.
- [3] C. Geertz, "Deep hanging out," *The New York review of books*, vol. 45, no. 16, pp. 69–72, 1998.
- [4] R. F. Yalch and E. Spangenberg, "An environmental psychological study of foreground and background music as retail atmospheric factors," in *AMA educators' conference proceedings*, vol. 54. Chicago: American Marketing Association, 1988, pp. 106–110.
- [5] L. M. Ward, J. Snodgrass, B. Chew, and J. A. Russell, "The role of plans in cognitive and affective responses to places," *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 1–8, 1988.
- [6] N. Hynes and S. Manson, "The sound of silence: Why music in supermarkets is just a distraction," *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, vol. 28, pp. 171–178, 2016.
- [7] U. Cartwright-Finch and N. Lavie, "The role of perceptual load in inattention blindness," *Cognition*, vol. 102, no. 3, pp. 321–340, 2007.
- [8] K. Falkenberg, M. L. Eriksson, E. Frid, T. Otterbring, S.-O. Daunfeldt, and G. F. Arfvidsson, "Auditory notification of customer actions in a virtual retail environment: Sound design, awareness and attention," in *Proceedings of International Conference on Auditory Displays*, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://smartech.gatech.edu/handle/1853/66330>
- [9] G. F. Arfvidsson, M. L. Eriksson, H. Lidbo, and K. Falkenberg, "Design considerations for short alerts and notification sounds in a retail environment," in *Proceedings of the Sound and Music Computing Conference*, 2021.
- [10] S. Marry and J. Defrance, "Analysis of the perception and representation of sonic public spaces through on site survey, acoustic indicators and in-depth interviews," *Applied Acoustics*, vol. 74, no. 2, pp. 282–292, 2013.
- [11] W. W. Gaver, "How do we hear in the world? Explorations of ecological acoustics," *Ecological Psychology*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 285–313, 1993.
- [12] G. Lemaitre and D. Rocchesso, "On the effectiveness of vocal imitations and verbal descriptions of sounds," *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, vol. 135, no. 2, pp. 862–873, 2014.
- [13] J. F. Gemmeke, D. P. W. Ellis, D. Freedman, A. Jansen, W. Lawrence, R. C. Moore, M. Plakal, and M. Ritter, "Audio set: An ontology and human-labeled dataset for audio events," in *2017 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*. IEEE, 2017.
- [14] B. L. Giordano, R. de Miranda Azevedo, Y. Plasencia-Calaña, E. Formisano, and M. Dumontier, "What do we mean with sound semantics, exactly? a survey of taxonomies and ontologies of everyday sounds," *Frontiers in Psychology*, vol. 13, 2022.
- [15] M. A. Cohen, T. S. Horowitz, and J. M. Wolfe, "Auditory recognition memory is inferior to visual recognition memory," *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, vol. 106, no. 14, pp. 6008–6010, 2009.
- [16] R. N. Shepard, "Recognition memory for words, sentences, and pictures," *Journal of Verbal Learning and Verbal Behavior*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 156–163, 1967.
- [17] T. Salvador, G. Bell, and K. Anderson, "Design ethnography," *Design Management Journal (Former Series)*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 35–41, 1999.
- [18] K. Baxter, C. Courage, and K. Caine, *Understanding your users: a practical guide to user research methods*. Morgan Kaufmann, 2015.
- [19] R. Teague and G. Bell, "Getting out of the box: ethnography meets real life: applying anthropological techniques to experience research," in *Usability Professionals' Association 2001 Conference*, 2001.
- [20] V. Braun and V. Clarke, "Using thematic analysis in psychology," *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 77–101, 2006.